

PECULIARITIES OF THE EFFECT OF TRAUMEL C ON THE CLINICAL COURSE OF PURULENT INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION

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ABSTRACT

The number of patients with purulent inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region is increasing. During the last decade the growth of scientific interest to the problem under study has been marked. Inflammatory maxillofacial region diseases one of the main observed signs of heavy course of the disease complication of which can be acute odontogenic mediastinitis, meningitis, sepsis, sinus thrombosis of dura mater. As a consequence, the number of lethal outcomes increases, which, according to various authors, can range from 25% to 55% especially when the inflammatory process is generalized, leading to septic shock, where the probability of a lethal outcome increases to 80%.

Purpose of the study: Evaluation of the effect of Traumel C in the treatment of patients with purulent inflammatory processes of the maxillofacial region

Introduction. Patients with purulent inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region account for about 10-20% of surgical patients attending dental clinics and over 60% of patients receiving specialised medical care in the departments of maxillofacial surgery. Patients admitted to these departments with a diagnosis of abscess or phlegmon account for 30% to 70% of the total number of patients. According to various authors, between 30% and 40% of dental beds are occupied by patients diagnosed with odontogenic

osteomyelitis. Medical advances in the study of the etiology and pathogenesis of inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region (TMF) have allowed the development of new methods of treatment and diagnosis. However, the prevalence of the pathology has not tended to decrease and the treatment process remains complex and lengthy, not insured against the development of complications. An odontogenic focus is a source of endogenous infection and can cause visceral pathology. One of the main factors in the occurrence of pyoinflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region is chronic stress, eating disorders, alcoholism, drug addiction, which leads to changes in the nonspecific and

immunological reactivity of the organism. Treatment of patients with purulent inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region is increasing and is not losing its relevance, which requires a comprehensive approach, which requires surgical and conservative methods of treatment aimed at combating microorganisms of cocciogenesis general intoxication of the body, stimulation of regeneration processes. Much attention in recent years in the special literature focuses on the use of drugs that limit the impact on the body of adverse factors. Such factors include purulent inflammation and related intoxication. One such drug is the peptide Deltaran synthesized by domestic scientists, which has an analgesic, detoxifying and adaptive effect. However, in the available literature we have not found any information about the use of Traumel C in acute pyo-inflammatory processes. The issues of modern diagnostics, prognosis and treatment of maxillofacial phlegmon are not solved, and the available scientific literature doesn't contain the publications devoted to the comparative analysis of its effectiveness and peculiarities of its use in maxillofacial surgery. In our research we have developed a rational complex of treatment of purulent inflammatory processes of the maxillofacial region with the use of Traumel C.

Materials and methods of investigation. For the study of patients with purulent inflammatory diseases of maxillofacial region, it is appropriate to use patients with this pathology. We studied 44 patients with purulent inflammatory diseases of maxillofacial region who were treated in Samarkand City Hospital during the period 2017-2020. The study was conducted in two phases. The first phase assessed the pharmacoepidemiology of drugs used in the treatment of patients with

acute purulent inflammatory diseases of maxillofacial region. At the second stage of the work the structure and resistance profile of pathogens isolated in patients with purulent inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region were studied.

Results of the study. The main pharmacological properties of Traumel C include: anti-inflammatory, anti-exudative, regenerative, analgesic, immunomodulatory, hemostatic effects. These properties are determined by the presence in Traumel C 14 components of plant and mineral origin. Mercurius solubilis Hahnemanni and Echinacea provide indirect antiviral and antibacterial immunomodulatory effects; Hepar sulphuris supports and improves cell respiration, redox processes and strengthens the vascular wall; Aconitum napellus and Arnica montana increase vascular tone, Hamamelis eliminates venous congestion, prevents blood clots, Millefolium helps stop bleeding, Aconitum, Arnica, Chamomilla, Hamamelis, Hypericum provide pain relief, Arnica, Calendula, Echinacea, Symphytum activate regenerative processes, helping to complete the inflammatory process. The complex of components in Traumel C helps to reduce the activity of enzymes such as elastase, cathepsin B, collagenase, $\alpha 1$ - protease, which protects the structure of connective tissue from their damaging action. This property is relevant because it contributes to the prevention or reduction of destructive phenomena in inflammatory processes, especially of autoimmune genesis. The mechanism of action of Traumel C differs from NSAIDs in that NSAIDs inhibit the enzyme cyclooxygenase in the arachidonic acid cycle, which reduces prostaglandin synthesis, thereby reducing manifestations

of pain and swelling, but leads to unwanted complications from the gastrointestinal tract and cardiovascular system. Traumel C, without inhibiting the arachidonic acid pathway, directly blocks cytokines by affecting their production and also promotes the expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines. Traumel C therefore has a powerful anti-inflammatory effect and at the same time does not have such negative side effects as NSAIDs. Thus, Traumel C optimises the course of the inflammatory process and ensures its complete resolution. The inclusion of Traumel C in the treatment of inflammatory diseases that require glucocorticoids makes it possible to reduce the dosage of hormonal drugs, and in some cases to eliminate their use. Evidence of a pronounced anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anti-edematous, regenerating effect are the results of the studies below. Some researchers have confirmed that Traumel C ointment allows a significantly quicker return to normal physical activity and that pain relief and reduction of swelling are more pronounced than with diclofenac.

Form and regimen for purulent inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region

Period of acute manifestations after acute manifestations have subsided
Solution for injection 1 ampoule 1-2 times a day #3-5 1 ampoule 1-3 times a week
Intra-, intra-, intra- and peri-articularly
Ointment, gel Apply to the affected area up to 5-6 times a day Apply to the affected area up to 3 times a day. Can be administered by phonophoresis Sublingual tablet 1 tablet every 15 min for 2 hours. If

necessary, repeat on day 2-3, 1 tablet 3 times a day The results of our study have shown that the treatment of various types of degenerative disorders, traumatic and inflammatory diseases using Traumel C (solution for injection) confirms its high effectiveness of the drug in monotherapy.

Conclusions: Traumel C has a number of advantages: no analogues in composition and spectrum of action, has an excellent tolerability and safety profile, has no side effects typical of NSAIDs, is used in different age categories, including in children from birth. Long-term use is possible, without addiction or withdrawal syndrome. In addition, Traumel C is available in different dosage forms (injections, tablets, ointment, gel), which makes it possible to choose the most convenient form and to combine the forms in an optimal way. For example, in an acute situation, you can start treatment with injections, and when the condition improves, switch to tablets or ointment/gel. If necessary, a combination with conventional standard therapy and other complex biological preparations that enhance anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anti-edema, detoxifying, immunomodulatory effects of Traumel C (Lymphomyozot, Viburkol, Echinacea Compositum C, Gynecohele, Metro-Adnex-Ingel, Gastrikumel, Hepel, Renel etc.) is possible. Thus, the complex biological preparation Traumel C is a new effective tool in the therapy of inflammation, affecting all phases of the inflammatory process and optimising its course, which leads to a quick and complete recovery of the patient.

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